

Platform to Decision-Making in Sustainable Tourism and Landscape Protection Based on Signal Detection

Vojtěch Novák

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
novakvojtech@pef.czu.cz

Michal Stočes

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
stoces@pef.czu.cz

Lukáš Kovář

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
kovarlukas@pef.czu.cz

Miloš Ulman

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
ulman@pef.czu.cz

Jan Jarolímek

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
jarolimek@pef.czu.cz

Jan Masner

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
masner@pef.czu.cz

Karel Kubata

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
kubata@pef.czu.cz

Eva Kánská

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic
kanska@pef.czu.cz

Abstract— In agricultural and forestry activities, there are decision-making dilemmas in tourist-attractive areas, for example, whether to give priority to tourism or to preserve the quality of the living and agricultural environment. To make decisions about these questions, it is important to get real traffic data, and that is what this article is about. presented a module for a data platform that can collect and analyse data about spa forest visitors using Bluetooth and Wi-Fi signals from users' smart devices. The module consists of sensors that are deployed in the field and a data platform module that processes, stores, and visualizes data using NodeRED, PostgreSQL DBMS and Grafana. The module also provides an external API that enables the connection of other applications. The module was tested in the real environment of the Spa Forests. for a period of eight months. These are natural areas that offer various services to visitors. A basic analysis of the data was carried out, especially the preferred length of stay and frequency of visits. Some issues and limitations of the module were also identified, such as the need to filter out stationary devices that skewed the data and security risks with respect to visitors' personal information. In an extreme case, visitors' health status can be inferred, which could threaten their privacy and security. Implications of these findings for the design and management of spa forest services are discussed and directions for future work suggested.

Keywords—data platform, module, sensor integration, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Grafana, Node-RED, visitor counting,

I. INTRODUCTION

People counting is the task of estimating the number of individuals in a given area or scene. It has many applications in fields such as ecology, forestry[1], tourism[2]–[4], and wildlife management[5]. However, traditional methods of people counting, such as manual surveys or video analysis, are often costly, time-consuming, and inaccurate. In addition, in the case of video analysis, it is common to use neural network models, which must first be trained on many desired detection objects, while inference from these models is usually computationally intensive and some of them cannot operate in

real time[6]. Therefore, there is a need for more efficient and reliable ways of counting people in various environments.

A novel method for counting people is to use wireless devices, such as mobile phones or laptops, that are equipped with wireless communication modules, such as Wi-Fi or Bluetooth. These devices can transmit or receive radio signals that carry data, over the wireless medium. By capturing and processing these radio signals, it is possible to infer the presence and number of people who carry such devices in each area or environment.[7]

In addition to the sheer number of devices, it is possible to detect other information about the smart device that the user has active - for example, the name of the device (which can usually be used to determine the specific model) or, for example, the manufacturer of the wireless chipset that is in the device.[8], [9]

This method has several advantages over other traditional methods that use dedicated sensors, such as cameras, infrared sensors, or ultrasonic sensors. First, wireless devices are ubiquitous and cheap, which means that many people own one or more of these wireless devices. Second, wireless devices can operate in various scenarios, such as indoor or outdoor, crowded or sparse, static or dynamic, while the detector of these devices does not require too much configuration. Third, wireless signals can penetrate walls and other obstacles, which enables people counting in occluded or non-line-of-sight situations, where vision-based methods cannot work well.

This paper introduces a module for a data platform that collects and visualizes data from smart devices of spa forest visitors. The module uses sensors, NodeRED, a database, visualization tool Grafana, and an API. The module was tested practically for eight months and showed good performance. The paper also analyses the data and shows the visitors' habits, as well as some issues and risks with data filtering and device identification. The paper has following sections: related

studies, module architecture, data analysis, results and discussion with suggestions of future research.

II. OVERVIEW OF STUDIES

Several studies have explored the use of smart devices for people counting in different scenarios, for example how WiFi signals can be used for different purposes, such as monitoring changes during COVID-19, counting occupancy in smart buildings, using different techniques to capture and analyse Wi-Fi probe requests, which are wireless packets that devices send to discover nearby Wi-Fi networks. S. Sun et al. [10] uses smartphones and wearable devices to collect probe requests from users in different countries and extract features related to their mobility and sociality. B. S. Çiftler et al. [11] uses Wi-Fi Pineapple equipment to passively collect probe requests from devices in a university building and apply a filtering technique to localize users within occupancy zones. R. Rusca et al. [12] uses Wi-Fi Pineapple equipment to actively collect probe requests from devices in a city and examine the characteristics of the probe requests, such as the frequency, the duration, and the fields. The authors show the potential and the challenges of using Wi-Fi signals for various applications, such as public health, energy management, surveillance, and privacy.

As for Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), the study by Münch and Schleif [13] aims to develop a device-free passive human counting system that does not require the people to carry any active device or participate in a localization process. Authors use BLE beacons that are placed under the seats in a lecture room and measure the fluctuations in the received signal strength indicator (RSSI) caused by the presence of humans. The study achieved an accuracy of about 82% with an average room occupancy of about 30 attendees. The study by Gong and Aty [14] aims to estimate the pedestrian and bicyclist count of intersection by using BLE scanners that can capture the media access control (MAC) addresses of nearby devices such as smartphones and smartwatches. The study validates proposed system by comparing it with video footage and achieve an average absolute percentage error of 6.35%.

A. Data platform

The collection of data on forest visitors through smart device detection involves the use of various sensors and devices that generate heterogeneous and complex data streams. To effectively process and analyse these data streams, a suitable platform should be able to integrate both data acquisition from different sources and data storage, retrieval, and visualization. By integrating these functionalities, the platform can enable the seamless transformation and aggregation of the raw data into meaningful and actionable information. Moreover, the platform can also generate interactive and informative visualizations that can facilitate the understanding and communication of the data insights to different audiences.

Such a platform is usually referred to as „Data platform“, which is an interface for data exchange and use among users and stakeholders in a domain or across domains. Data platforms can enable open science by offering management instruments for data quality, governance, access, analytics, and engagement. Data platforms can differ in their technology, domain [15], and openness [16]. Data platforms can be assessed by their functionality, usability, interoperability, and sustainability. [17]

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Data platform module architecture

The architecture of the data platform and its context is shown in the figure 1 below. As the data platform are often of a considerable size, only one part of it (module) is plotted in the following figure, which deals with the collection, storage, display and evaluation of data associated with the Spa Forests site, all the sensors illustrated in the diagram are close to the administration building in this area of the spa forests, which have a total area of 2,190 hectares. From the diagram it is evident that sensors of environmental variables (temperature, pressure, humidity, wind speed and direction, etc.) as well as a Bluetooth and WiFi frames sensor – Cisco Meraki – are installed in the locality. Since the sensors are from different manufacturers and communicate in different ways, the received data from these sensors needed to be captured, transformed, and stored – for this purpose, the NodeRED software was used, which contains individual snippets that transform the input data stream and then store the transformed data in a database. The data stored in the database can then be viewed in Grafana (which contains individual dashboards for each sensor). API is also available if data from the platform is needed in an external application.

Figure 1 Data platform module diagram

Storing the data in a data platform has the advantage of allowing different stakeholders to access and use the data for

various purposes. For instance, the owner of the land where the sensors are installed can monitor the environmental conditions and optimize the land use, as well as detection on approximately how many people are visiting forest, for example. This can help them improve their management practices and increase their revenue. On the other hand, the researchers from the university that developed and maintains the data platform can perform more advanced analyses and extract valuable insights from the large and diverse data sets collected by the sensors. This can help them advance their scientific knowledge and contribute to solving environmental and social challenges.

B. Data analysis

The analysis required collecting data from a Meraki device that was installed in the spa forest area. The device could detect both Wi-Fi and Bluetooth signals from nearby devices. The data collection spanned over eight months, from 8:00 p.m. on October 5, 2022, to 6:00 p.m. on June 15, 2023. During this period, the device recorded 1,772,652 Wi-Fi sightings and 971,321 Bluetooth sightings to the database. These sightings corresponded to 15,573 distinct Wi-Fi devices and 94,309 distinct Bluetooth devices, based on their MAC addresses. However, the devices were only pseudo-distinct, as they could change their MAC addresses periodically to prevent tracking and identification.

Figure 2 Grafana dashboard - Bluetooth

Basic data visualization and evaluation was done using Grafana, where one dashboard was created for this purpose, as is shown in Figure 3 and Figure 3. The use of Grafana is appropriate when data is scarce and when it is more convenient to interpret the data immediately, or for those users who wish to see the results immediately and in a user-friendly

manner. For analysing large amounts of data, Grafana may not be entirely ideal, and it is usually preferable to use offline analysis methods (where the data is first downloaded using the API and then statistically processed). Offline analysis will also enable the interpretation of what information can be derived from this big data and how the Grafana dashboard should be adjusted afterwards.

Figure 3 Grafana dashboard – Wi-Fi (MAC addresses anonymized)

IV. RESULTS

The filtered (pseudo)unique Wi-Fi devices were also subjected to an analysis to ascertain the identity of the manufacturer of the Wi-fi chipset. The MAC address of the device, which consists of six octets, can be used to reveal the manufacturer. The first three octets are called the Organizationally Unique Identifier (OUI) and they are allocated to different hardware manufacturers by the IEEE, which is the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers.

In the collected dataset, Wi-fi devices from 172 distinct manufacturers were observed; the most frequent ones and their device occurrence rates are displayed in the table that follows:

TABLE I. MOST FREQUENT WI-FI DEVICE MANUFACTURERS

<i>Manufacturer name</i>	<i>Device count</i>
MediaTek Inc.	8 701
Samsung Electronics Co., Ltd	1 199
Unknown	1 014
Xiaomi Communications Co Ltd	940
ALPSALPINE CO, LTD	489
HUAWEI TECHNOLOGIES CO., LTD	370
Motorola Mobility LLC, a Lenovo company	345
InPro Comm	336
Samsung Electro-Mechanics (Thailand)	236
Wistron Neweb Corporation	224
Apple, Inc.	223
Texas Instruments	106
Murata Manufacturing Co., Ltd.	102
Garmin International	102
Liteon Technology Corporation	96
Intel Corporate	96
Sony Corporation	55
Continental Automotive Systems Inc.	47
LG Innotek	46
Spreadtrum Communications (Shanghai) Co., Ltd.	41
Huawei Device Co., Ltd.	38
ESSYS	35
Motorola (Wuhan) Mobility Technologies Communication Co., Ltd.	34
Continental Automotive Czech Republic s.r.o.	32
Ford Motor Company	32

From the table above, it can be observed that some manufacturers of the devices could not be identified from the MAC addresses collected. This is because OUIs of these MAC addresses were not recorded in the IEEE manufacturer database, which assigns a unique identifier (OUI) to each manufacturer. As shown in the table above, a single category called “Unknown” (on the third row) was used to group these devices. There were 1,014 pseudo-unique devices that were included in this category.

The raw data of the detected Wi-Fi beacons are plotted in Figure 4, showing the distribution of the beacons by month, day and hour. The heat map reveals that there was a surge of Wi-Fi beacons in February 2023, especially during the night hours. The analysis attributed this to the installation of several stationary devices - Wi-Fi access points - near the detection equipment. These devices were identified as Ubiquiti products based on their MAC addresses. Figure 4 on the right side also displays the filtered unique devices from the Wi-Fi beacons, obtained by setting the sampling window to 1 hour instead of device’s default 30 seconds. This allowed to eliminate duplicate MAC addresses and count the number of pseudo distinct devices in each time slot. The filtered data indicates that the area attracts more visitors in the afternoon and during the summer months.

Figure 4 Wifi - beacons vs filtered devices

Figure 5 BLE detected vs filtered devices.

A similar procedure was applied to the data from the Bluetooth devices, as shown in Figure 5. However, the Bluetooth data may still contain a lot of duplicates if some devices change their MAC addresses during the sampling period.

The names of the detected Bluetooth devices were also analysed. Out of 94,309 pseudo-unique devices, only 3,372 had a name assigned, and there were 1,758 distinct names. Among these names, only six devices had a personalized name (the user modified the default device name). The most prevalent Bluetooth devices were smart bracelets (Mi Smart Band 4, Mi Smart Band 5, Mi Smart Band 6), followed by smart watches (Vivoactive 3, Amazfit GTS, Amazfit GTR, Amazfit T-Rex, Amazfit GTS2 mini), which also showed the highest diversity in terms of models and manufacturers.

Other detected devices included smart bikes (Bosch E-bike), cyclo-navigation devices (Edge 830, Edge 530), cyclo-computers (EOX R500, Nyon-367, Edge Explore, MegaC GPS, ROX 4.0), professional drones (Inspire 2), professional cameras (Canon EOS 90D, EOS R6, EOS 850D, Nikon D500), portable speakers (Charge 4, Charge 5, Sharkk 2o), GPS units and car diagnostics (Teltonika, OBDEleven 2).

The infotainment system of a nearby caravan was also detected by the measuring apparatus.

Some of the personal devices detected were smart toothbrushes (Oral B, Oclean X, Oclean Z1).

Some of the devices detected could potentially compromise the privacy of the individuals in the vicinity of the measuring apparatus, such as hearing aids or glucometers (devices from company Dexcom were detected).

The heat plots suggest a positive relationship between the number of Wi-Fi and Bluetooth devices. That is, if there are higher numbers of Wi-fi devices at certain hours, there will also be higher numbers of Bluetooth devices as well. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the two variables (Bluetooth and Wifi device count) is 0.77.

The similarity of the results can serve as a tool for verifying the correct functioning of the technology. Or there is scope for saving costs for sensor equipment, where you only need to choose one technology.

V. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

This paper designed and implemented a module for a data platform that can collect and analyse data from smart devices in spa forests. The module consists of sensors, a NodeRED tool, a database, a Grafana tool, and an external API.

The module was tested in spa forests for eight months. The results showed that the module was reliable and useful, and that the data provided insights into the visitors of the spa forests, such as their (pseudo) number, frequency, duration, and preferences.

Using a modular approach, the data platform can include the module of this study and numerous other modules that deal with data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

However, the data collection and analysis also faced some challenges and limitations. One of them was the need to filter out the signals from stationary equipment. Another challenge was the ethical and privacy issues related to the identification of smart devices and their owners. The data showed that many

visitors did not change the default names of their devices and some devices had in its name unique identifier which made it possible to track users or to infer their health status or personal characteristics. This poses risks for the privacy and safety of the visitors.

As for future work, several directions are suggested: To increase the accuracy and reliability of the data, more sensors and more advanced filtering techniques should be used (e.g., machine learning). If more collection units are used, it would also be useful to roughly define occupancy zones, like those defined by B. S. Çiftler et al.[11] To enhance the data visualization, more interactive and user-friendly dashboards should be created. To expand the scope of the research, other types of environments or devices should be applied to or explored by the module. It would also be advisable that the data from the Meraki device, which detects signals from Wi-Fi and Bluetooth devices, could be combined with other sensors already present in the module, which measure environmental variables such as temperature, humidity, and pressure. This weather data could provide some other insight into the and preferences of the visitors of spa forests (llpkv.cz).

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